

Application of Field Desorption and Electron Impact Mass Spectrometry and N.M.R. Spectroscopy in the Study of Flavonoid-O-Glycosides

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The field desorption mass spectra of chrysoeriol 7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (1) and chrysoeriol 7-O- β -D-glucopyranosidyl (2 \rightarrow 1)-D-aplofuranoside, graveobioside-B (2) at different emitter heating currents are described. The molecular ion, or the pseudo-molecular ion appeared as the base peak in each case and hence enabled determination of their molecular weights. The presence of fragment ions due to cleavage of the sugar units provides considerable assistance in the identification of the sugar(s), particularly of the terminal sugar of the diglycoside (2) and high resolution electron impact spectra proved useful in identifying structural features in the parent aglycone. The occurrence of (M + 23 Na) $^{+}$ and/or (M + 39 K) $^{+}$ ions in some of the field desorption spectra due to the presence of sodium, and/or potassium salts of the glycosides as impurities, can assist in the distinction between (M) $^{+}$ and (M+1) $^{+}$ ions. The N.M.R. spectra of the hexaacetate (4) of (1), the octaacetate (5) of (2) and the triacetate (6) of their common aglycone, chrysoeriol (3) are also discussed.

UPON electron-impact ionization (E.I.) underivatized^{1,2}, peracetylated³ and permethylated^{4,5} flavonoid-O-glycosides are known to show initial fragmentation of their sugar moiety, while underivatized flavonoid-O-glycosides eliminate the saccharide unit and give only the mass spectra of the aglycones with practically no molecular ion peaks^{1,2,6}. Until recently the use of E.I./M.S. of peracetylated flavonoid-O-glycosides was limited to the verification of their molecular weights⁷, but a few reports on the E.I. spectra of a number of permethylated^{7,8} and perdeuteriomethylated^{9,10} flavonoid-O-glycosides have now appeared. In many cases, however, the molecular ions of these derivatized flavonoid-O-glycosides were very weak (or were not observed); such low intensity peaks may be confused with the background ion peaks in the mass spectrometer or with those arising from impurities in the sample¹¹.

The utility of field ionization (F.I.) mass spectrometry and field desorption (F.D.) mass spectrometry in the analysis of thermally labile and difficultly-volatile compounds is well established^{6,11-14}. The F.I. and F.D. spectra of these compounds usually show very strong molecular, and/or quasi-molecular ion peaks. F.I. has also been used in the study of complex mixtures¹⁵⁻¹⁸ and mixtures of underivatized coumarins^{19,20}, alkaloids^{20,21}, terpenes^{20,22} and insect secretions²³. The F.I. spectra exhibit some ions

due to thermal fragmentations, but a large number of underivatized biologically important compounds are not amenable to E.I., F.I. or chemical ionization (C.I.) mass spectral study owing to their lack of volatility^{11,20}. F.D. has been found to overcome these difficulties^{1,11}, and this technique has been extensively utilized in the analysis of underivatized thermally labile and non-volatile compounds,^{6,11,13,20,23} alkali-metal salts^{6,11,13,24-26} and quarternary ammonium salts^{27,28} of organic substances. Recently Games¹¹, Beckey and Schulten¹³, and Games and Schulten⁶ have applied F.D. mass spectrometry to the study of the iso-flavanone-O-glycoside, naringin, the flavanone-O-glycoside, hesperidin and the flavone-O-glycoside, rutin. We have now studied the F.D. spectra of the underivatized flavone-O-glycosides (1) and (2) at different wire currents. The spectra showed strong molecular ion peaks together with some meaningful fragmentations.

Recently the E.I. spectra of a mixture of perdeuteriomethylated graveobioside (2) and apin have been reported⁷, but their molecular ions were of very low intensity. Moreover, the origin of an intense ion peak in the spectra of both is not clearly understood⁷. The E.I. spectra of underivatized (1) and (2) gave neither their molecular ions nor any fragmentation of their sugar units; the spectra obtained in both cases were identical with the spectrum of their common aglycone, (3) itself (see Table 1), whose spectrum does not appear

TABLE I

 E. I. Spectrum of (3), m/e (%)

301 (18),	300 (100),	299 (5),	284 (2),	272 (3),	271 (2)		
270 (1),	257 (7),	229 (7),	154 (2),	153 (19)	152 (3)		
149 (3),	148 (10),	137 (2),		133 (8),	124 (4),	123 (4),	115 (10)

$m/2e$ 136 (4.47).

Scheme 1

to have been recorded previously. The base peak was the molecular ion of (3) which followed two fragmentation pathways (Scheme 1). In one case, it underwent the retro-Diels-Alder reaction giving ions (i), (ii) and (iii), the most prominent of the three arising as a result of hydrogen transfer²⁰. The other fragmentation pathway was initiated by the loss of carbon monoxide furnishing the ion (vi), which was associated with a considerable doubly-charged ion²⁰ at m/e 136.

Subsequent fragmentation of the daughter ions is illustrated in Scheme 1, and further discussion on the topic is felt unnecessary since it is well documented in the literature²⁰.

The F.D. spectrum of the *O*-glucoside (1) recorded at a wire current of 18 mA is shown in Fig. 1. In contrast to the E.I. spectrum, the F.D. spectrum showed an $(M+1)^+$ ion at m/e 463 as the base peak and a very

FIG. 1. Field desorption mass spectrum of chrysoeriol 7-*O*- β -D-glucopyranoside (1)
 Solvent, methanol/acetone. 18 mA emitter heating current.

strong molecular ion at m/e 462. The spectrum is structurally more informative since it also exhibited some fragmentation of the glucose moiety. (The ions at m/e 404 and 58 (glyoxal) are attributed to cleavages (b) and (c) of the glucose ring between the ring-oxygen and C-1" and between C-4" and C-5"). Cleavage (a) between C-1" and the glycosidic oxygen gives rise to the ion at m/e 300 (protonated aglycone⁶). The ion at m/e 433 may be attributed to the loss of formaldehyde from the $(M+1)^+$ ion with hydrogen transfer (cleavage d). The spectrum also exhibited an ion at m/e 485 $(M+^{23}\text{Na})^+$ formed by cationization in the polar solvent^{6,11,31}, which was probably due to salt contamination during its preparation. In addition to other methods^{11,32}, the presence of this ion may also assist in the distinction between $(M)^+$ and $(M+1)^+$ ions^{15,33}, since its intensity varies with variation in polarity of the solvent and wire current²⁶. Thus at 17 mA this ion was totally absent and at 19 and 20 mA its intensity was only 2% (see Table 2). At the higher wire currents a number of new ions were also observed indicating further fragmentation of the aglycone and the sugar unit of (1) (see Table 2).

The F.D. spectrum of the *O*-diglycoside (2) run at 20 mA (Fig. 2a) showed its molecular ion as the base

Compound	Emitter wire current	Solvent	m/e (%)		
(1)	19 mA	methanol/acetone	485 (2)	464 (17)	463 (70)
			462 (100)	433 (3)	432 (2)
			301 (4)	300 (11)	272 (1)
			271 (1)	270 (2)	58 (2)
(1)	20 mA	methanol/acetone	485 (2)	464 (26)	463 (99)
			462 (100)	433 (1)	432 (1)
			302 (5)	301 (8)	300 (29)
			271 (4)	270 (1)	58 (1)
(2) m.p. 214-216°	21 mA	methanol/water with traces of acetone	595 (38)	594 (21)	566 (18)
			566 (33)	565 (43)	564 (100)
			462 (21)	271 (21)	133 (99)
			133 (90)	103 (18)	85 (64)
			59 (21)		

FIG. 2. Field desorption mass spectrum of chrysoeriol 7-O- β -D-glucopyranosidyl (2 \rightarrow 1)-D-apiofuranoside (2), m. p. 214—216° solvent, methanol/water/traces of acetone. (a) 20mA emitter heating current, (b) 18mA emitter heating current

peak at m/e 594, and is clearly more informative than its E.I. spectrum. The ions at m/e 462 and 150 are assigned to cleavages (b) and (c) respectively, of the (2→1) linkage with hydrogen transfer. This type of cleavage may be useful in the identification of the terminal sugar of a flavonoid-*O*-oligosaccharide. The spectrum also exhibited the loss of formaldehyde (cleavage d) from both (M)⁺ and (M+1)⁺ ions with proton transfer giving rise to the ions at m/e 564 and 565, respectively. It also showed an ion at m/e 617 (M + ²³Na)⁺ which may again assist in the distinction between (M)⁺ and (M+1)⁺ ions, since it disappeared when the spectrum was re-run at 18 and 21 mA (see Fig. 2b and Table 2).

The spectrum at a wire current of 21 mA also provided some other interesting variations and useful information. Although the intensities of both (M)⁺ and (M+1)⁺ ions were quite low, it showed the alternative cleavage of the (2→1) linkage giving rise to the ion at m/e 133 which underwent successive loss of formaldehyde (with 1,6-hydrogen shift), water and acetylene, generating the ions at m/e 103, 85 and 59 respectively (see Scheme 2). This type of cleavage is also very useful for the identification of the terminal sugar unit of a flavonoid-*O*-oligosaccharide.

Another point of interest is the fact that 18 mA the spectrum did not exhibit any ion due to the aglycone, but it still showed some fragmentation of the sugar

units (Fig. 2b). Furthermore, under F. D. conditions (1) and (2) did not undergo retro-Diels-Alder reaction³³.

During the isolation of the glycoside (2) (m.p. 214-216°) from a new natural source, a compound (m.p. 207-208° and slightly less soluble in ethanol than the former) was encountered³⁴. These were thought to be identical on the basis of their other physical, spectral and chemical characteristics³⁴. The F. D. spectrum of the lower-melting compound (Fig. 3) was almost identical with that of the higher-melting one (Fig. 2) but the former showed an ion at m/e 633 (+³⁹K)⁺, in addition to the common (M + ²³Na)⁺ ion at m/e 617. The observed difference in melting point and solubility may well be due to the presence of potassium salts of the glycoside in the lower-melting sample as salt contaminations incorporated during the process of isolation³⁴.

The NMR spectra of (5) and (6) showed some variations in chemical shift assignment and splitting pattern from those reported in an earlier publication³⁵ (without mentioning the solvent and standard used).

The protons at C-6 and C-8 of (4), (5) and (6)³⁶ gave rise to two doublets ($J = 2.5$ Hz) at 6.74-6.90 and 7.05-7.40 respectively (Table 3). Their C-5' protons also appeared as a doublet ($J = 8$ Hz) centred at 7.19, whereas the C-2' and C-6' protons resonated at downfield positions; the former as a singlet at ca. 7.42 and the latter as a doublet ($J = 8$ Hz) centred at 7.50. The glycosyl methine protons attached to a carbon atom bearing an acetoxy group or two ether linkages resonated at a lower field than the methine and methylene protons next to a single ether group or methylene protons next to an acetoxy function³⁷. The C-1' methine protons of (4) and (5) gave rise to a complex multiplet rather than a doublet, presumably as a result of free rotation of the 7-*O*-glycosidyl moiety with respect to the flavone nucleus, thus confirming the fact that C-6 and C-8 do not bear any substituent³⁸. The aliphatic acetoxy proton signals occurred at 1.97-2.14 whereas the aromatic acetoxy proton signals occurred at 2.32-2.45, the C-5 acetoxy protons always appearing at the most downfield position³⁸.

FIG. 3. Field desorption mass spectrum of chrysoeriol 7-*O*- β -D-glucopyranosidyl (2→1)-D-apiofuranoside(2), m.p. 207-208°

Solvent, methanol / water / traces of acetone. 20 mA emitter heating current

TABLE 3—NMR. SPECTRAL ASSIGNMENTS OF COMPOUNDS (4), (5) and (6)

Assignments	(Chemical Shifts are on the δ -scale)		
	Compound (5)	Compound (4)	Compound (6)
3-H	6.60 s	6.60 s	6.60 s
6-H	6.76 d ($J=2.5$ Hz)	6.74 d ($J=2.5$ Hz)	6.90 d ($J=2.5$ Hz)
8-H	7.08 d ($J=2.5$ Hz)	7.05 d ($J=2.5$ Hz)	7.40 d ($J=2.5$ Hz)
2'-H	7.43 s	7.40 s	7.42 d ($J=1.5$ Hz)
5'-H	7.18 d ($J=8$ Hz)	7.19 d ($J=9$ Hz)	7.19 dd ($J=1.5$ and 8Hz)
6'-H	7.50 d ($J=8$ Hz)	7.50 d ($J=9$ Hz)	7.50 d ($J=8$ Hz)
1'',3'',4'',1''',2'''-H	5.05-5.32 b. s.	2.28-5.40 b.s. (1'',2'',3'',4''-H)	—
2'',5''-H	4.00 m	4.24 m (5''-H)	—
6''-H	4.24 m (2H)	4.30 (2H)	—
4'''-H	4.58 s (2H)	—	—
4''''-H	4.20 m (2H)	—	—
5-OAc	2.44 s (3H)	2.45 s (3H)	2.45 s (3H)
4'-OAc	2.35 s (3H)	2.35 s (3H)	2.32 s (3H)
7-OAc	—	—	2.32 s (3H)
2''-OAc	—	2.05 s (3H)	—
3''-OAc	2.14 s (3H)	2.07 s (3H)	—
4''-OAc	2.09 s (3H)	2.07 s (3H)	—
6''-OAc	2.05 s (3H)	2.05 s (3H)	—
2''',3'''-OAc	2.03 s (6H)	—	—
4''''-OAc	1.97 s (3H)	—	—
3'-OMe	3.94 s (3H)	3.97 s (3H)	3.91 s (3H)

The C-2' acetoxy protons of the acetates of C-6 and C-8 glucosyl flavones^{3,7} and the C-2 acetoxy protons of 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-*O*-acetyl-1-*O*-(indol-3-ylacetyl)-D-glucopyranose^{3,9,40} are known to resonate at a higher field than the other aliphatic acetoxy protons as a result of shielding by their aromatic nuclei. It may be pointed out here that the C-2' acetoxy protons of (4) did not experience any such shielding effect and resonated along with the other aliphatic acetoxy protons at 2.05-2.07.

Experimental

F. D. spectra were recorded with a Varian CH 5D mass spectrometer fitted with a combined F.D./F.I./E.I. source using benzonitrile activated tungsten emitters. Spectra were obtained via a Varian 620i computer. The solvent was methanol/acetone for (1) and methanol/water with traces of acetone for (2). The optimal emitter wire currents were 16 to 22 mA and the maximal current was 25 mA.

The E. I. spectrum of (3) and the high resolution E. I. spectrum of (2) were also obtained with the Varian CH 5D mass spectrometer and Varian 620i computer, at 70 eV (source temperature 220°), and those of (1) and (2) were recorded on a Hitachi RMU6 instrument at 75 eV, and 50 mA.

The NMR spectrum of (5) was recorded on a Varian HA 100 spectrometer and those of (4) and (6) on a Varian A 60 instrument. Deuteriochloroform was used as the solvent with tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. Chemical shifts are given on the δ -scale, and *s*, *d* and *m* indicate singlet, doublet and multiplet, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Dr. R. S. Kapil (Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow) for the E. I. M. Spectra of (1) and (2), and the NMR spectra of (4) and (6).

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